

Thin-Film PZT-Based Multi-Channel Acoustic MEMS Transducer for Cochlear Implant Applications

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Abstract—This paper presents a multi-channel acoustic transducer that works within the audible frequency range (250-5500 Hz) and mimics the operation of the cochlea by filtering incoming sound. The transducer is composed of eight thin film piezoelectric cantilever beams with different resonance frequencies. The transducer is well suited to be implanted in middle ear cavity with an active volume of $5\text{ mm} \times 5\text{ mm} \times 0.62\text{ mm}$ and mass of 4.8 mg. Resonance frequencies and piezoelectric outputs of the beams are modeled with Finite Element Method (FEM). Vibration experiments showed that the transducer is capable of generating up to 139.36 mV_{pp} under 0.1 g excitation. Test results are consistent with the FEM model on frequency (97%) and output voltage (89%) values. Device was further tested with acoustic excitation on an artificial tympanic membrane and flexible substrate. Under acoustic excitation, 50.7 mV_{pp} output voltage generated under 100 dB Sound Pressure Level (SPL). Output voltages observed in acoustical and mechanical characterizations are the highest values reported to the best of our knowledge. Finally, to assess the feasibility of the transducer in daily sound levels, it was excited with a speech sample and output signal was recovered. Time-domain waveforms of the recorded and recovered signals showed close patterns.

Index Terms—Acoustic transducer, fully implantable cochlear implant, MEMS, thin film piezoelectric.

I. INTRODUCTION

OUR ears are magnificent organs that enable us to perceive ambient sounds from the faintest flapping of an insect to the extremely loud roaring of spacecraft launch through

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the hearing chain: eardrum, ossicles, and the cochlea. They make the ear the best acoustic sensor by providing broad frequency selectivity (20 Hz – 20 kHz) and dynamic range (0 – 140 dB SPL). Unfortunately, according to World Health Organization (WHO) around 466 million people suffer from hearing loss worldwide, and 34 million of them are children. It is estimated that 900 million people will be diagnosed with hearing loss by 2050 [1]. Hearing loss is classified as mild, moderate, severe or profound, depending on the hearing threshold of the patient. Severe to profound type sensorineural hearing loss (more than 90 dB SPL) is caused by irreversibly damaged sound sensing hair cells in the cochlea. Cochlear implant (CI), which is a surgically implanted device, is required to recover this type of hearing loss [2]. Today's CIs perform the hearing action with an external microphone to sense incoming sound, which is then converted to biphasic pulses through a microprocessor. These pulses bypass the healthy outer and middle parts of the natural hearing mechanism and directly simulate the auditory nerves in the cochlea via specialized electrodes. CIs can achieve reasonable performances in difficult speech tests [3] and high-quality music perception [4]. However, conventional CIs have major drawbacks affecting users' life quality such as: (1) risk of

damaging outer components especially when exposed to water or sweat, (2) MRI incompatibility, (3) aesthetic concerns particularly in children and young patients, (4) daily battery replacement \ recharging, and (5) high cost [2], [5]. These problems can be eliminated by Fully Implantable Cochlear Implant (FICI) systems. FICI concepts eliminate the external components of CI such as the active microphone, transmitter, and external battery. Instead, FICI comprises of an implantable acoustic sensor, low power stimulation circuits, and an implantable battery. One of the prominent fully implantable cochlear implant concepts, FLAMENCO: A Fully-Implantable MEMS-Based Autonomous Cochlear Implant, combines a multi-channel acoustic transducer [6]–[8], a piezoelectric energy harvester [9], an ultra-low power interface circuit [10] and a commercial CI electrode [11]. All parts of the system can be implanted inside the middle ear cavity to meet the FICI requirements. Fig. 1 shows the overall diagram of the FLAMENCO concept.

In this paper, an implantable acoustic transducer of FLAMENCO concept, which can be a milestone for FICI applications, is presented. The design of this transducer is inspired by an ancient music instrument ‘mbira’ that consists of several beams corresponding to different resonance frequencies. Using this paradigm, we achieved mechanical filtering of the ambient sound into frequency bands, without consuming any power. This structure is realized using MEMS fabrication to a scale that can fit into the middle ear while relying on the vibration of natural hearing mechanism to sense incoming sound. This feature efficiently replaces active microphones and outer parts of a conventional CI, which have so far been the main bottlenecks of FICI systems. In the next part, we explain design considerations of the implantable acoustic transducer, state-of-the-art transducers in the literature and design methodology of the multi-channel acoustic transducer. MEMS fabrication steps of the system, implementation, characterization, and testing under daily circumstances of the transducer are also presented in this paper.

II. DESIGN AND MODELING

In sensorineural hearing loss, the natural vibration of the hearing chain is still functional and enables collecting ambient sound with an implantable transducer. This existing feature provides an opportunity to overcome the drawbacks of cochlear implants by using a middle ear implantable acoustic transducer. However, this approach has five main restrictions:

- 1) Dimensions: Transducer has to be placed on eardrum or ossicles to sense incoming sound. Nonetheless, the limited volume of middle ear (1 cm^3) [12] and area of the ear drum ($9 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$) [13] restrict the dimensions and structure of the transducer. Therefore, a dense and compact structure is needed for the implantable transducer. This restriction is the main obstacle that inherently limits other requirements such as frequency range and output voltage.
- 2) Mass: Besides the physical dimensions of the middle ear cavity and eardrum, additional mass or force loading on the hearing mechanism affects the natural vibration char-

Fig. 1. Illustration of fully implantable cochlear implant concept, FLAMENCO in the middle ear [11].

acteristics. This effect has been studied in the literature, and in-vivo studies show that adding 25 mg mass on the eardrum causes a 3 dB reduction in the amplitude of the vibration [14].

- 3) Number of channels: The overall frequency spectrum of the transducer must cover the daily acoustic band with an adequate number of channels. Sound perception quality depends on the number of channels, frequency distribution, and filtered frequency bands of each channel. Conventional cochlear implants include 4 to 22 channels to filter the incoming sound and to stimulate the neurons. Recent studies show that sound perception rate saturates up to 8 channel [15]–[17].
- 4) Frequency range: Human ear can perceive sound in a wide frequency range (20 Hz – 20 kHz) with a very high dynamic range (0 - 140 dB SPL). These properties cannot be achieved for cochlear implants with today’s technology. Nonetheless, the basic daily sound perception can be recovered. Human voice mostly includes frequencies between 250 Hz to 4kHz [18]. Lower frequencies (<250 Hz) includes vibrations produced by the body and higher frequencies (4 to 8 kHz) are essential for speech perception in a noisy environment [19].
- 5) Output voltage and dynamic range: The output signal of the transducer excites the neural interface circuit, which stimulates the auditory neurons in the cochlea. These specialized interface circuits generate biphasic pulses for stimulation at multi channels with low power consumption. The minimum input level of this low power interface circuit is $100 \mu\text{V}$ which is the minimum limit for the transducer to stimulate the neurons [10].

In the literature, capacitive and piezoelectric methods have been investigated to implement implantable acoustic transducers to overcome these five restrictions. Young *et al.* [20] attached MEMS capacitive accelerometer-based transducer on the umbo in the middle ear with a readout circuit and could detect 60-dB SPL at 500 Hz, 35-dB SPL at 2 kHz and 57 dB SPL at 8 kHz. However, capacitive sensing methods

require readout circuitries due to their low output levels. Their readout circuit consumes high power for FICI applications (~ 4.5 mW). This is higher compared to the piezoelectric approaches. Because, the state-of-the-art low power interface circuitry to stimulate the neurons in the cochlea consumes less than $500 \mu\text{W}$ power [10]. Moreover, the output level of piezoelectric approaches can be further boosted by upgrading stress levels on the structure; this makes the piezoelectric approach more feasible for implantable applications.

Piezoelectric methods have been studied as middle ear and intracochlear implantations [21]. Multi-channel spiral-shaped AlN piezoelectric cantilever array was studied by Udvardi *et al.* [22]. Lower frequency band (300-700 Hz) of the hearing spectrum is covered with 16 channels and they generate 3.0 – 9.6 mV under 1 g acceleration. Even though, they proposed upper portion of the frequency range can be covered with the same approach, sensing low dB sounds in the upper frequency band was a problem due to the reduction of stress levels.

Jang *et al.* [23] designed a piezoelectric based artificial basilar membrane that includes ten channels to filter ambient sound into frequency bands in the range of 10-37 kHz. This structure could generate 3.55 mV under 112.4 dB sound excitation. Recently, same group presented another structure that is an artificial basilar membrane based on an AlN piezoelectric cantilever array [24]. This design consisted of an 8-channel distributed on the upper side of the hearing band (2.92-12.6 kHz) and generated 4.06 mV at 7.04 kHz under 101.7 dB sound pressure. Unfortunately, neither of these designs were able to generate sufficient output voltage to provide a wide enough dynamic range for FICI applications.

Zhao *et al.* demonstrated a different approach by developing an AlN piezoelectric intracochlear acoustic transducer that consists of an array of 4 cantilever beams. The implanted transducer in a guinea pig cochlea can generate up to $79.7 \mu\text{V}$ under 95 dB SPL in a wide frequency range [25]. The problem of this distinctive method is generated low output voltage. Sensing these low output levels requires interface circuitries with a low noise amplifier (LNA) which increases power consumption beyond a feasible budget.

Wang *et al.* [26] reported a highly sensitive piezoelectric mobile acoustic sensor (PMAS) for machine learning biometrics. This flexible acoustic sensor was designed for mobile applications and includes seven channels at biomimetic frequency bands. The sensitivity (52 mV/Pa) and the signal to noise ratio (up to 92 dBV) of this sensor is superior with respect to previous reports. However, the structure covers 130 mm^2 which is much greater than the available area in the middle ear. Their study also shows that resonance frequencies of the channels diverge from audible range when its dimensions are downsized. Therefore, this structure cannot be used for cochlear implant applications.

As a result, none of the structures in the literature can satisfy the given requirements for a fully implantable CI system. On the other hand, they demonstrated the opportunity of piezoelectric devices to generate voltage by using the vibration of ossicles and tympanic membrane. By synthesizing the outcomes in the literature and improving the

Fig. 2. Structure of the multi-channel acoustic transducer with and without mechanical test frame.

outputs in COMSOL model, we designed a multi-channel thin film PZT based piezoelectric transducer. This transducer meets the requirements of FICI applications without requiring any readout circuitry. Therefore, it can be a milestone for implantable transducers for FICI applications.

The aforementioned problems can be solved by using the array of cantilever beam structures with tip masses. This structure is capable of high deflection and stress range while its manufacturing is relatively easy. This structure can work with a wide dynamic range and output voltage. Silicon based cantilever structure's resonance frequency mainly depends on its stiffness and tip mass. In order to reach to the lower frequencies with cantilever structures, stiffness can be decreased by increasing the length of the cantilever. However, this method cannot be applied due to area and volume limitations. Therefore, adding mass on the tip of the cantilever is inevitable to lower the resonance frequencies and compact structure. Tip mass usage also increases the mechanical stress on the beam and boosts the generated output voltage. By this way, lower frequencies and wide frequency ranges can be covered in a denser structure.

Increasing the number of channels increase the power consumption of processing the sound for each channel. Furthermore, the limited volume and the loading mass of the hearing system also restrict the channel number. For these reasons, 8-channel is the most convenient for current FICI applications. In conventional cochlear implants, center frequencies of these channels are placed between 250 Hz to 6 kHz, which are linearly distributed below 1200 Hz and logarithmically above 1200 Hz [27]. In the proposed system, a similar frequency distribution is applied. Fig. 2 shows the array of cantilever beams structure which fulfills the design restrictions.

The feasibility of piezoelectric sensing on the membrane has been proved previously [8]. However, there are several constraints to select the material for implantable MEMS transducer. The material must generate high output voltage in a small area to overcome the minimum input level of

TABLE I
PROPERTIES OF THIN FILM PLD -PZT

Thickness (μm)	ϵ_{33} (1kHz, 0V)	$\tan\delta$ (1kHz, 0V)	Polarization Pr ($\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$)	$-\epsilon_{31}$ (C/m^2)
1	2000	0.01-0.02	20	7.7

Fig. 3. Fabrication flow of the multi-channel MEMS transducer.

the interface circuit; work in a wide dynamic range without losing its piezoelectric properties; be compatible with fabrication without increasing the complexity and preserve these properties throughout its lifetime. Under these circumstances, thin film piezoelectric materials promise higher performance for sensing applications and fill less volume compared to bulk materials. Among thin film piezoelectric materials, Pulsed Laser Deposited PZT (Lead Zirconate Titanate) is preferred due to its ferroelectric and piezoelectric properties which are shown in Table I [28]. Moreover, recent studies show that PZT based sensors for specific applications can exhibit superior SNRs (up to 92 dBV), which is vital for clear sound recognition [26]. The thickness of the material is another design parameter which affects the generated output characteristic. Studies of the supplier company, Solmates BV, show that using 1 μm PLD-PZT is suitable for beam structures [29]. Therefore, a 1 μm piezoelectric layer has been used in this study.

In order to implement the transducer with given restrictions (dimension, mass, number of channels, frequency range and output voltage), we modeled the structure with Finite Element Analysis software COMSOL Multiphysics. During simulations, mechanical vibration characteristics were monitored under constant acceleration to obtain required output levels (Simulation model is explained in detail in Supplementary Materials). In vitro test results of umbo displacement characteristics were taken as a reference for acoustic characterizations [23]. This structure includes 8 silicon-based cantilever beams with silicon tip masses to reach the required frequency range. 8-channel system, with frequencies placed at 300, 600, 600, 1200, 1600, 2200, 3200 and 4800 Hz as in conventional cochlear implants, can fit into 5 mm \times 5mm \times 0.62 mm and weight only 4.8 mg without testing frames. They are well below the limitations and give flexibility to other parts of a

Fig. 4. Mechanical characterization test setup of a multi-channel transducer.

fully implantable system i.e., acoustic energy harvester and 3D packaging [30]. Besides the size and mass limitations, output signal level is arranged to generate the minimum input level of the interface circuit at daily hearing levels and provide a 60 dB dynamic range.

III. FABRICATION

Transducers are fabricated on a 4-inch (100 orientation) SOI wafer (15 μm device/2 μm oxide/600 μm handle layers). The device layer of the SOI wafer defines the cantilever thickness hence the stiffness of the structure, and handle layer forms the tip mass which are the critical parameters for defining resonance frequencies of the channels. Therefore, using an SOI wafer provides controllable resonance frequency for the transducer. Fig. 3 shows the fabrication process flow. First, 500 nm thick thermal oxide is deposited for lateral electrical isolation between the electrodes. Then, 10 nm Ti and 100 nm Pt are sputtered as the bottom electrode; Pt is selected as bottom electrode because of its high thermal conductivity and its stability at high temperature environment during PZT deposition [31]. Thin film PLD-PZT is deposited by Solmates (SMP-700 PLD) and patterned by a custom etchant provided by the firm. The Pt bottom electrode is patterned by using hot aqua regia solution. On top of the electrodes, 1 μm Parylene - C is deposited for vertical isolation between electrodes and patterned by using Reactive Ion Etching (RIE). 30 nm Cr and 400 nm Au layer is used as top electrode of the transducer. Remaining Parylene - C layers outside the top electrode areas are stripped using RIE. Cantilever and tip mass are formed with oxide etching in RIE and silicon etching in deep reactive ion etching (DRIE) from both sides of the wafer. All fabrication steps are completed below 115 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is well below the poling temperature (200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) of the PLD PZT.

Only deformation on the structure was occurred due to the thickness differences between buried oxide (2 μm) of the SOI

Fig. 5. Experimental and simulation results of the multi-channel transducer.

and thermal oxide (500nm) on the device layer, and long cantilevers were bent slightly upward after releasing. In further fabrication, oxide layer thicknesses were arranged equally to minimize bending.

The fabricated transducer includes two concentric test frames as shown in Fig. 2. The outer test frame has wide electrodes to make contact with pogo pins, and it is used for mechanical vibration tests and electrical resonance characterization. Inner test frame is suitable for acoustic tests. It has small electrodes and can be used with connecting wire bonds to a special parylene substrate for system level integration. These frames are connected to each other with short silicon bridges, but they can easily be separated with a diamond cutter if needed, making the structure compatible with both testing scenarios.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fabricated transducers are characterized with mechanical, and acoustic test setups. First, devices were tested on a shaker table under constant acceleration (0.1 g). Fig. 4 shows the holder set up for electrical connections of transducers via pogo pins. The electrical measurement is conducted via Data Acquisition Board (DAQ) and LabView for autonomous measurement. Under these conditions, the transducer can generate up to 139.36 mV_{pp} at 316 Hz, which is the highest output voltage for a similar size transducer in the literature to the best of our knowledge. Other channels' output voltage varies between 7.18 and 86.15 mV_{pp} at frequencies between 647.3 Hz and 5575 Hz [6]. These output levels are consistent with post simulation results of the established finite element analysis in COMSOL Simulation. Table II shows that experimental results are in good agreement with simulations on frequency (97 %) and output voltage (89 %) values. Fig. 5 shows experimental and simulation results of all channels, proving the equivalence of the performance.

After the vibration test, the outer test frame of transducer is removed, and transducer is connected to the special flexible parylene substrate via wire bonds. Fig. 6. shows the acoustic test setup with transducer attached to the substrate. In order to prevent collusion of the cantilevers to the carrier during vibration experiments, it is glued to parylene with small epoxy bumps. Parylene provides connection flexibility and enables integration of the system with artificial tympanic membrane for acoustical tests. During the acoustic tests,

Fig. 6. Acoustic test setup for multi-channel acoustic transducer with acoustic holder, parylene carrier.

a special hollow tube whose dimensions is defined based on the ear canal dimensions is used. 300 μm PDMS membrane, which reproduce the basic vibrational characteristic of human tympanic membrane (TM), is clamped at the end of the tube. By this way, clamped membrane's first resonance frequency is obtained about 1 kHz similar to the TM and its vibration amplitude obtained inside the reported limits up to 8 kHz [32] (Structure and the vibration characteristic of the PDMS membrane and artificial ear canal are explained in Supplementary Materials).

A single tone sinusoidal acoustic wave is applied to the artificial ear canal and PDMS membrane by using an insert earphone (Etymotic ER-2) which is driven by an audio amplifier (Denon-PMA-520AE). This combination can provide flat output characteristics in the audible frequency range. Sound level of the applied signal is kept constant by using a probe microphone (Etymotic ER-7C) placed near the earphone. This single tone amplified sound signal vibrates the membrane thuswise the transducer. Transducer filters this signal mechanically by the channel whose frequency range is matched with the applied signal. Meanwhile, Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) (Polytec MSA-050) system measures the displacements and sensitivities of the beams while DAQ (NI CompactDAQ) records the output voltage of the transducer. With this setup, frequency spectrum of the transducer is obtained between 50 dB and 100 dB SPL. Fig. 7 shows the acoustic response of the second

Fig. 7. Acoustic test results of the transducer under different SPLs.

TABLE II
SHAKER TABLE TEST AND SIMULATION RESULTS OF THE TRANSDUCER [6]

Channel Number	Simulation		Shaker Table	
	Frequency (Hz)	Voltage (mV _{pp})	Frequency (Hz)	Voltage (mV _{pp})
1	316.4	141.0	316.4	139.4
2	648.0	90.1	647.3	86.2
3	990.1	45.3	988.3	42.8
4	1325.0	23.9	1321.0	22.2
5	1714.9	16.7	1735.8	14.7
6	2429.2	21.6	2452.3	20.1
7	3524.3	38.8	3497.8	36.6
8	5574.0	7.6	5767.2	7.2

Fig. 8. Sound test setup of the transducer.

channel. Also, maximum output voltages and sensitivities of the channels are given in Table III and Table IV. Sensitivities are measured between 50 and 100 dB SPL and averaged to minimize errors.

Acoustic test results show that the transducer can generate up to 50.69 mV under 100 dB SPL on channel 2, and other channels' output performances are varying between 5.62 mV to 40.73 mV. Note that 100 dB level is the output limit of the utilized test setup. Transducer was also tested at 1 g vibration without getting damaged which means it can work up to 120 dB SPL. For 50 dB SPL input level, transducer generates output potential up to 210 μ V. Thus, we reached to target in most of the channels by exceeding the minimum input level of the interface circuit, 100 μ V. The sensitivity of the transducer is also an important parameter for realizing the hearing action. The presented transducer's sensitivity range is between 2.93 to 25.79 mV/Pa depending on the channel. Overall, the output voltage and sensitivity of the transducers shown in this work are the highest reported in literature, which is shown in detail in Table V. Sensitivities of channels 4, 5, 7, and 8 are lower concerning other channels. This difference

occurs due to the vibration characteristics of the artificial tympanic membrane. Fig. S5 in Supplementary Materials shows the vibration characteristic of the PDMS membrane and human TM with additional mass. Vibration characteristics show that loss levels in the vibration amplitude near the resonance frequencies of channels 4, 5, 7, and 8 are higher than the other channels. Therefore, sensitivities and quality factors of the channels are affected by the membrane characteristics.

In order to observe the performance of the transducer in daily activities, each channel of the transducer is tested by applying a speech signal in the setup shown in Fig. 8. Selected speech signal "A white silk jacket goes with any shoes" is a typical sentence utilized in hearing tests [33]. The speech signal is generated in MATLAB. Since each channel is excited separately, a specific control sequence is added at the beginning of the sentence to eliminate the phase difference between channels. Then, generated sound signals is played by a 5 W speaker, and the mean sound level is arranged to \sim 70 dB SPL, which is the average level of the home with a TV or small office [34]. Outputs of the channels are amplified

Fig. 9. Time-domain waveforms of the test sound and transducer output.

TABLE III
ACOUSTIC TEST RESULTS OF THE TRANSDUCER

Channel Number	Frequency (Hz)	Output Voltage (mV _{pp})					
		100 (dB)	90 (dB)	80 (dB)	70 (dB)	60 (dB)	50 (dB)
1	313.7	40.73	11.95	4.09	1.20	0.43	0.15
2	652.6	50.69	16.27	4.92	1.60	0.56	0.21
3	1004.0	20.51	6.51	2.10	0.67	0.24	0.09
4	1309.5	5.62	1.80	0.56	0.17	0.07	-
5	1916.2	12.42	4.12	1.24	0.44	0.15	-
6	2416.9	36.28	10.84	3.71	1.13	0.38	0.15
7	3626.9	7.52	2.39	0.78	0.26	0.09	-
8	5417.5	5.24	1.86	0.57	0.18	0.07	-

with a low noise amplifier (LNA), and a DAQ is used for recording the signal.

Output signals of the channels are imported in the MATLAB and with the help of the control signals, and aligned with each other to eliminate phase differences. After aligning the signals, they are combined to reconstruct the sentence sound. Filtered and reconstructed signal generates comparable waveforms. Fig. 9 shows the reconstructed speech signal and original test signal's time-domain waveforms. Although, covered bands of high frequency channels are limited, envelopes of the output and the input signals correlate with each other. Also, regenerated sound signal is intelligible as provided in supplementary files. This correlation and intelligibility of sound signal proves the feasibility of the transducer in real application.

In hearing devices, performance is defined by sound perception. Standard CIs use active microphones and electrical filters to provide high quality sound perception. This method enables to cover all audible frequency bands but consumes power. Filtering sound mechanically to mimic the hair cells with frequency selective structures do not need power supplies but could not cover the whole hearing band in lower sound levels. For instance, 3rd channel of the multi-channel thin film acoustic transducer can generate the minimum input level of the interface circuit, 100 μ V, throughout 342 Hz (center frequency is at 1004 Hz) at 70 dB SPL, while 8th channel covers 145 Hz under same conditions. Sound level differences between the channels also affects the sound

TABLE IV
SENSITIVITIES OF THE CHANNELS

Channel Number	Frequency (Hz)	Quality Factor	Sensitivity	
			mV/Pa	μ m/Pa
1	313.7	202.4	20.04	32.05
2	652.6	118.7	25.79	13.65
3	1004.0	22.9	10.73	14.76
4	1309.5	23.2	2.93	1.44
5	1916.2	153.4	6.68	9.46
6	2416.9	329.3	18.14	3.51
7	3626.9	15.9	4.01	2.42
8	5417.5	87.7	2.95	1.84

TABLE V
PERFORMANCES OF THE ACOUSTIC TRANSDUCERS

Study	Number of Channels	Frequency Range (kHz)	Excitation	Output Level (mV)	W×L×H (mm ³)
[8]	1	1.325	100 dB	~40	5×5×0.5
[22]	16	0.3-0.7	1 g	9.6	32×32×0.55
[23]	10	10-37	112.4 dB	3.55	6.5×6.5×0.35
[24]	8	2.9-12.6	101.7 dB	4.06	2.5×2.5×0.6
[26]	7	0.83-3.6	120.1	430	3-10×20×0.01
This Study	8	0.25-5.5	0.1 g	139.4	5×5×0.62
			100 dB	50.7	
			120 dB*	~500 ^a	

^a Extrapolated from test results.

perception, but they can be equalized by the patient fitting system of stimulation interface circuits. Each channel of the CI has its own patient fitting and stimulation amplitude can be arranged. Another consideration regarding the output characteristics is high quality factor of the output signal which causes ringing effect in standard microphone applications. On the other hand, in the cochlear implants, Continuous Interleaved Sampling (CIS) sound processing strategy is used. This strategy provides sequential stimulation of channels at fixed frequency [10]. Hence, channels get relaxation time between the stimulation intervals.

The presented structure includes 8-channel in the audible frequency range and only covers a small portion of the dimension limitations for a middle ear implantable transducer. Therefore, the structure has a wide design margin to extend the frequency range and improve sound perception. The same methodology can increase channel numbers and arrange the resonance frequencies, which can be achieved by stacking transducer layers on each other to improve the outcomes. Furthermore, stacking the structures can be used to shrink the structure to be implemented in a smaller area. The middle ear has the flexibility to apply these changes.

Handicaps of the system arise when the system is desired to work with a low power stimulation circuit because the main disadvantage of the system is the minimum detectable sound level of the stimulation circuit. Due to this level, the transducer cannot sense a portion of the audible frequency bands under low sound pressure levels. Vacuum packaging of the structure or reducing the minimum input level of the circuit can overcome this problem.

For practical use of the transducer in cochlear stimulation, the system needs a sound level fitting system to improve the sound perception. High quality factor in filtering system causes nonequivalent output levels for same sound pressures at different frequencies. In literature, interface circuits don't include such an input fitting system for single channel or multi-channel transducer systems. These non-ideal signal levels will affect the sound perception quality of the implants. Consequently, the effects of this gap and solutions must be studied as future work for both CIs and FICIs.

In order to be an implantable device, the transducer must be justified by many different tests from many aspects. The first step toward this aim is the packaging of the transducer. The transducer will be packaged, then encapsulated with parylene-C, which will isolate the device from body fluids and tissues. In this way, system will be biocompatible. The biocompatibility of parylene-C is well documented, and the parylene coatings comply with USP Class VI Plastics requirements and ISO 10993 standards to be used in medical devices [35]. After packaging, the device must be tested under in vitro and in vivo conditions for long term stability and durability to be an implantable device.

V. CONCLUSION

A thin film piezoelectric multichannel acoustic transducer for FICI applications is designed with inspiration from ancient music instrument, fabricated by using MEMS methods, systematically characterized, and experimentally adapted for daily usage. Results show that the transducer achieves the highest output levels in the literature. Also, implantable multi-channel acoustic transducer has been tested with a speech signal for the first time in the literature to the best of our knowledge. Output of the transducer generated similar waveforms with input sound signal at the daily sound level. These outcomes prove the feasibility of mechanically filtering the sound into frequency bands without power consumption. This feature extends the usage of the implant in one charging cycle by reducing the total power consumption and enables to eliminate the outer parts of the implant can provide flexibility to the user. The transducer demonstrated in this work is a candidate to be a milestone for middle ear implantable acoustic transducers.

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